

Green Marketing Mix and Social Media Information on Green Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty

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Abstract

The importance of ecological issues has grown in today's economic environment. Environmental issues are significant to many nations, and sustainable growth is currently a prominent corporate objective. Social media advertising is becoming a primary mode of communication as more and more customers actively use social media for product searches and purchases. The research aims to examine the effect of green marketing mix and social media information on green customer satisfaction and green customer loyalty. This also analysed the mediating effect of customer satisfaction between green mix, social media information and green customer loyalty. The study focused on quantitative research design and primary data collected by convenience sampling method from 340 green marketing customers of Kathmandu Valley. Measurements and structural equation modeling were used to convert data into comprehensive knowledge. Results shows direct impact of Green product value has a substantial influence on green customers' satisfaction and insignificant effect on green customer loyalty. The mediating result revealed that satisfied customers are loyal. The study discovered, however, that social media information and green pricing had no discernible impact on green consumer satisfaction and loyalty. Green businesses may get an advantage by including green marketing mix strategy into their entire marketing plan to satisfy green customer and make loyal.

Keywords: *green customer satisfaction and green customer loyalty, green marketing mix, social media*